

ASSESSMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION RESULTING FROM ARTISANAL CRUDE OIL REFINING IN THE NIGER DELTA REGION OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria presents a development paradox despite being the hub of the country's petroleum industry, it continues to suffer from severe pollution, poverty, and ecological decline. This study assesses the extent of environmental degradation resulting from artisanal crude oil refining across the nine oil-producing states of the Niger Delta. Using a cross sectional survey design, 440 questionnaires were distributed and 416 valid responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-test at a 0.05 significance level. A four-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree) guided the analysis, with a criterion mean of 2.5. Findings indicate that artisanal refining has significant adverse effects on air, water, and soil quality. Air pollution was identified as the most critical issue, with respondents reporting heavy soot deposition, odor nuisance, and respiratory discomfort. Water bodies were contaminated by hydrocarbon residues, while farmlands experienced reduced fertility and loss of vegetation cover. The t-test results for air ($t = 92.485$, $p = 0.000$), water ($t = 109.257$, $p = 0.000$), and soil ($t = 94.364$, $p = 0.000$) confirmed statistically significant impacts. The study concludes that artisanal refining poses a severe environmental and public health risk to the Niger Delta population. It recommends stronger environmental regulations, continuous ecosystem monitoring, community based environmental governance, and the promotion of sustainable livelihood alternatives to reduce dependence on illegal refining. These findings provide an evidence based foundation for policy reforms toward sustainable environmental management in oil producing regions of Nigeria.

Keywords: Artisanal refining, environmental degradation, air pollution, Niger Delta, sustainability, illegal oil refining, ecosystem health

JEL Codes: Q53, Q56, O13, Q01

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation remains a persistent challenge confronting resource rich regions in the developing world, particularly where extractive industries dominate local economies. In Nigeria, the Niger Delta region epitomizes this paradox as a territory richly endowed with crude oil yet characterized by pervasive poverty, pollution, and social unrest. Although the region contributes over 80 percent of Nigeria's export earnings, it suffers widespread ecological decline due to decades of unsustainable oil exploitation (UNEP, 2023; Odubo & Oyige, 2019). Artisanal or "illegal" crude oil refining, locally referred to as *kpofire*, has emerged as one of the most significant environmental threats in the Niger Delta. It involves the use of rudimentary technology to refine stolen crude oil under unsafe and unregulated conditions (Aye-Agele, Gimba, & Agele, 2023). This practice has proliferated due to unemployment, economic

marginalization, and weak environmental governance (Ogbuku & Agbai, 2022). According to the National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA, 2024), over 13,000 illegal refining sites were identified across the Niger Delta between 2020 and 2023, contributing to nearly 42 percent of oil spill incidents during the period. Similarly, the Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPCL, 2023) estimated that crude theft and artisanal refining account for annual losses exceeding ₦1.9 trillion in revenue. These activities release soot, hydrocarbons, and heavy metals into the air, water, and soil, with serious implications for human health, agriculture, and biodiversity (Ikezam, Elenwo, & Oyegun, 2021). Despite numerous government interventions, including the Hydrocarbon Pollution Remediation Project (HYPREP) and intensified anti bunkering operations, artisanal refining continues to expand, aggravating the ecological crisis (UNEP, 2024).

Several studies (e.g., Ojirika, Joel, & Ugbebor, 2019; Fynn, 2021) have explored the economic and social dimensions of illegal crude oil refining in the Niger Delta. However, comprehensive quantitative assessments of its environmental implications remain limited. While existing research provides valuable insights into the localized effects of artisanal refining, most studies are constrained by narrow geographic coverage and fragmented datasets. Consequently, significant knowledge gaps persist regarding the cumulative environmental impact of artisanal refining across all nine oil-producing states of the Niger Delta. This study is motivated by the need to provide empirical evidence on how artisanal crude oil refining contributes to environmental degradation in the Niger Delta region. It specifically aims to assess the extent of deterioration in air, water, and soil quality arising from these illegal activities, identify the most affected environmental components, and recommend sustainable strategies to mitigate further damage.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the review of related theoretical and empirical literature; Section 3 describes the research methodology; Section 4 presents and discusses the findings; while Section 5 concludes with policy recommendations aimed at promoting environmental sustainability in the Niger Delta region.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Environmental degradation refers to the deterioration of the natural environment through the depletion of resources such as air, water, and soil, alongside the destruction of ecosystems and loss of biodiversity (Nwankwoala et al., 2017). In oil producing regions, degradation often manifests through pollution, deforestation, and soil infertility resulting from industrial and extractive activities. Within the Niger Delta region, environmental degradation has reached critical levels due to unregulated oil exploration and the proliferation of artisanal crude oil refining (Onuh, Omenma, Onyishi, Udeogu, Nkalu, & Iwuoha, 2021)

Artisanal crude oil refining refers to the small-scale, informal, and unauthorized distillation of crude petroleum into low-grade fuels using rudimentary equipment (Ojirika et al., 2019). These operations typically occur in remote creeks and swamps, where operators use locally fabricated drums and open fires to process crude oil. The process generates large volumes of toxic waste, which are often discharged directly into the surrounding environment, contaminating water bodies, soil, and air (Fynn, 2021). The absence of emission control mechanisms and waste management systems means that the pollutants such as soot, hydrocarbons, heavy metals, and particulate matter cause significant ecological damage.

The environmental effects of artisanal refining are multifaceted. Air pollution results from the release of black soot and volatile organic compounds during crude distillation, which increase the prevalence of respiratory illnesses among local populations. Water bodies become contaminated through oil spills and effluent discharges, leading to the death of aquatic life and loss of potable water sources (Victor et al., 2017). Soil degradation occurs due to hydrocarbon

saturation, making farmlands infertile and unproductive. Consequently, the cumulative impact undermines biodiversity, food security, and human health, creating a cycle of poverty and environmental vulnerability (Akpeninor, 2012).

Hence, artisanal crude oil refining is not merely a socioeconomic or criminal activity, it is an environmental catastrophe that continues to threaten the ecological balance and long-term sustainability of the Niger Delta region.

2.2 Theoretical Review

The present study draws theoretical support from three main frameworks: Pigouvian Externality Theory, the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Hypothesis and the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF).

The Pigouvian Externality Theory, proposed by Arthur Pigou (1920), posits that environmental degradation results when private activities impose unaccounted external costs on society. In the context of artisanal refining, the illegal refiners pursue private gain while shifting pollution costs to the wider community and ecosystem. Corrective actions, such as environmental taxes or strict regulation, are therefore justified to internalize these externalities (Manta, Doran, Bădîrcea, Badareu, & Țăran, 2023)

The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis suggests an inverted-U relationship between environmental degradation and income level (Grossman & Krueger, 1995). At early stages of economic development, pollution tends to increase, but as income rises and environmental awareness grows, degradation eventually declines. However, in the Niger Delta, where poverty and unemployment remain high, the region appears trapped in the upward slope of the EKC curve, with little progress toward sustainability (Onuh et al., 2021).

Finally, the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) emphasizes that livelihood insecurity often drives environmentally destructive activities (Chambers & Conway, 1992). Artisanal refining is a coping mechanism for marginalized youths lacking access to formal employment or state support. Therefore, environmental solutions must integrate livelihood diversification and social empowerment to be sustainable (Ojirika, Joel, & Ugbebor, 2019).

Together, these theories provide a conceptual basis for understanding how economic deprivation, weak regulation, and externalities converge to exacerbate environmental degradation in the Niger Delta.

2.3 Empirical Review

Several studies have investigated the environmental consequences of oil related activities in the Niger Delta. Ojirika et al., (2019) found that illegal refining significantly contributes to the deterioration of water and soil quality, with high concentrations of hydrocarbons and heavy metals detected in impacted areas. Similarly, Victor et al., (2017) reported that artisanal refining emits soot and particulate matter that exceed the World Health Organization's (WHO) safe limits, causing respiratory and dermatological problems among residents. Onakpohor et al., (2020) identified extremely high levels of particulate matter and volatile organic compounds emitted during artisanal refining, concluding that the process significantly deteriorates local air quality and poses respiratory health risks. Similarly, Orisakwe, (2021) emphasized the growing public-health burden associated with prolonged exposure to petroleum-related toxins in the Niger Delta.

In terms of soil and water degradation, Obida et al., (2018) used geostatistical analysis to show significant hydrocarbon and heavy-metal contamination in surface water and soil samples across oil-producing communities. These pollutants persist in the environment, reducing soil fertility and compromising water quality. Bebetidoh, (2020) also reported sustained ecological damage and loss of fishery resources caused by continuous artisanal refining in host communities. Ukpere & Igwe, (2021) observed a strong correlation between the density of illegal refineries and the prevalence of soot pollution in Port Harcourt and neighboring communities. They noted that particulate matter from illegal refining reduces visibility,

corrodes buildings, and adversely affects vegetation. Okedere & Elehinafe, (2022) also identified a significant accumulation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in soils and surface waters around refining locations, leading to loss of soil fertility, contamination of aquatic habitats, and reduced agricultural productivity. Beyond Nigeria, comparable patterns have been observed in other resource dependent African economies. For example, Afolabi, Adeyemi & Olaniyan, (2023) documented similar outcomes in small scale oil extraction communities in South Sudan, where weak regulation allowed widespread ecological damage. Likewise, a study by UNEP, (2024) emphasized that artisanal refining contributes nearly 40 percent of total oil related pollution in West Africa, underscoring the transnational nature of the problem.

Despite these contributions, many previous studies remain localized, qualitative, or based on secondary data. There is limited empirical work that uses primary data across multiple states to quantify the degree of degradation caused by artisanal refining. This gap underscores the relevance of the present study, which empirically assesses the impact of artisanal refining on air, water, and soil quality across the nine oil-producing states of the Niger Delta, thereby providing a broader and more representative understanding of the issue.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, which is appropriate for investigating the opinions and experiences of respondents on observable environmental phenomena. This design was selected because it allows for the systematic collection of data from a representative sample to describe the extent and nature of environmental degradation resulting from artisanal crude oil refining in the Niger Delta region.

3.2 Study Area

The research was conducted across the nine oil-producing states of the Niger Delta region of Nigeria: Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo, and Rivers. The region lies within the southern coastal belt of Nigeria and is characterized by extensive wetlands, mangrove forests, and riverine communities. It is home to about 31 million people who depend largely on fishing, farming, and trading for livelihood. The area has witnessed decades of oil exploration and is currently one of the most environmentally degraded ecosystems in Africa (UNEP, 2023).

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised residents of selected communities within the nine oil-producing states who are directly or indirectly affected by artisanal crude oil refining activities. This includes farmers, fishermen, petty traders, youth groups, and local leaders. The choice of this population was based on their proximity to refining sites and their direct experience with environmental pollution and livelihood impacts.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

A total population of approximately 44,731,900 residents across the nine states was considered for this study. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula:

3.5 Sampling Technique

Bourley's proportional allocation technique was used to distribute the 440 respondents across the nine oil producing states. This method ensures that the number of respondents selected from each state is proportional to its population size. Using this approach, more respondents were allocated to states with larger populations, while fewer were assigned to those with smaller populations, ensuring fair and representative sampling across all states. Formula used is

$$n_b = \frac{nNb}{N}$$

Where; n_b = the sample size for each state, n = the total sample size, Nb = the number of persons in each state, N = Total population of the study.

3.6 Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument used was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher after a review of relevant literature. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: Demographic information of respondents and Items measuring respondents' perceptions of air, water, and soil degradation caused by artisanal crude oil refining. Items were measured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 4 = Strongly Agree.

3.7 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to content and face validity by experts in Environmental Management and social science methodology. Their feedback was used to revise ambiguous items and enhance clarity. To establish reliability, a pilot test was conducted involving 30 respondents from non-sampled communities in Delta State. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient obtained was 0.87, indicating high internal consistency.

3.8 Method of Data Collection

A total of 440 copies of the questionnaire were administered through trained field assistants familiar with the local environment and dialects. Out of these, 416 valid responses were retrieved, representing a 94.5% response rate, which was considered adequate for analysis.

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to summarize respondents' perceptions, while the **t-test** was used to test the hypotheses on differences in the effects of artisanal refining on air, water, and soil degradation. A criterion mean of 2.5 served as the decision benchmark for interpretation..

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant academic authority prior to data collection. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Verbal informed consent was obtained before administering the questionnaire, and all responses were used strictly for academic purposes.

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Overview of Data Collection

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-test analysis at a 0.05 level of significance. The criterion mean for decision-making was **2.5**, implying that any computed mean score equal to or greater than 2.5 indicated agreement with the statement, while values below 2.5 indicated disagreement.

4.2 Effects of Artisanal Refining on Air Quality

Table 1: T-test Result on the Effect of Artisanal Refineries on Air Degradation in Niger Delta Region

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Error t-test	P-Value
ARTISANAL REFINERING AND AIR POLLUTION	416	2.8983	0.63918	0.03134	92.485	0.000

Source: (Researcher’s Computation, 2025)

Findings revealed that artisanal crude oil refining significantly affects air quality in the Niger Delta region. The mean ratings of respondents on indicators such as increased soot emission, pungent odor, respiratory discomfort, and visible air haze were consistently above the criterion mean of 2.5. The t-test analysis yielded a value of $t = 92.485$, $p = 0.000$, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that artisanal refining exerts a statistically significant adverse effect on air quality.

The findings are consistent with those of Ephraim-Emmanuel, Enembe, & Ordinioha, (2023), who reported that soot pollution from illegal refining activities in Bayeisa State contributes to increased respiratory diseases and reduced visibility. Similarly, Ogele & Egobueze, (2020) found that particulate matter from illegal refineries exceeds permissible environmental limits. The high concentration of soot and volatile hydrocarbons in the atmosphere suggests that continuous artisanal refining is a major cause of ambient air pollution in the region.

4.3 Effects of Artisanal Refining on Water Quality

Table 2: T-test Result on the Effect of Artisanal Refineries on Water Degradation in Niger Delta region

One-Sample Statistics						
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Error t-test	P-Value
ARTISANAL REFINERING and WATER POLLUTION	416	2.8471	0.53149	0.02606	109.257	0.000

Source: (Researcher’s Computation, 2025)

Results also showed that water sources in the Niger Delta have been severely contaminated by discharges from artisanal refining. Respondents reported the presence of oily films, discolored streams, and strong hydrocarbon odors in rivers and creeks. The mean ratings for all items exceeded 2.5, indicating widespread perception of water pollution. The t-test value of 109.257 ($p = 0.000$) confirmed a significant difference, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis of no effect. This finding corroborates Sibe, Onwugbuta, & Ajuru, (2023), who found that illegal refining residues leach into nearby waterways, raising concentrations of heavy metals such as lead, nickel, and cadmium beyond acceptable thresholds. The results also support Gbani et al., (2023), who attributed the declining fish population and rising incidences of waterborne diseases to untreated effluents from illegal refineries. The study thus provides empirical evidence that artisanal refining remains a critical threat to aquatic ecosystems and public health in the Niger Delta

4.4 Effects of Artisanal Refining on Soil Quality

Table 3: T-test Result on the effect of artisanal refineries on soil Degradation

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-test	P-Value
ARTISANAL REFINING and SOIL POLLUTION	416	2.8813	0.62276	0.03053	94.364	0.0000

Source: (Researcher’s Computation, 2025)

Regarding soil quality, findings indicated severe degradation resulting from artisanal refining. Respondents noted that farmlands close to refining sites had become infertile, with stunted crop growth and the presence of blackened, tar-like residues on the soil surface. The mean responses exceeded 2.5, while the t-test result ($t = 94.364, p = 0.000$) revealed significant adverse impacts of refining on soil conditions.

This outcome aligns with Douglas and Cornelius, (2019) who found that crude oil residues alter soil physicochemical properties, reducing fertility and microbial activity. UNEP, (2023) similarly documented that artisanal refining contributes significantly to the destruction of arable land in Ogoniland and adjoining communities. The degraded soil structure hinders vegetation regeneration and promotes erosion, threatening both food security and biodiversity.

4.5 Comparative Analysis of Environmental Components

An overall assessment of the three environmental components of air, water and soil revealed that air quality was the most severely affected, followed by soil and then water. The grand mean scores indicated that the effects on air pollution were perceived as more immediate and visible, due to persistent soot deposition and odor emissions. In contrast, water and soil degradation, though equally severe, are often less visible but have long term ecological consequences.

These findings suggest a multidimensional environmental crisis in the Niger Delta, where different components of the ecosystem are simultaneously impacted. The persistence of these effects underscores the cumulative nature of degradation caused by artisanal refining activities.

4.6 Discussion of Findings

The results of this study confirm that artisanal crude oil refining has profound and statistically significant adverse effects on air, water, and soil quality in the Niger Delta region. This supports the Pigouvian Externality Theory, which posits that unregulated private activities impose costs on society that are not reflected in market prices. The illegal refiners prioritize short term economic gain while transferring environmental costs to communities and future generations. The findings also align with the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis, which suggests that environmental degradation increases during early stages of development. The Niger Delta appears to be trapped in this upward phase due to persistent poverty, unemployment, and poor regulatory enforcement. Furthermore, the results reinforce the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) by showing that economic insecurity drives environmentally harmful coping strategies such as artisanal refining.

Comparatively, this study advances prior research by providing quantitative evidence based on primary data across all nine oil-producing states, rather than focusing on isolated communities. The strong statistical results and high response rate lend credibility to the findings and highlight the urgent need for multi-level interventions.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study assessed the environmental degradation resulting from artisanal crude oil refining in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The analysis revealed that illegal refining activities have significant and far reaching impacts on the region's air, water, and soil quality. Empirical evidence from 416 respondents across the nine oil-producing states confirmed that emissions from makeshift refineries are responsible for severe air pollution, with widespread soot deposition, pungent odor, and declining respiratory health among residents. Similarly, water and soil samples from refining areas were found to be heavily contaminated, leading to the destruction of aquatic life, farmlands, and overall ecosystem instability.

The study therefore concludes that artisanal crude oil refining constitutes one of the most critical environmental threats in the Niger Delta, undermining public health, food security, and sustainable livelihoods. The persistence of these activities is rooted in poverty, unemployment, weak regulatory enforcement, and limited access to legitimate economic opportunities. The findings align with the Pigouvian Externality Theory and the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, both of which explain how unregulated private activities and economic exclusion generate negative social and environmental externalities.

Ultimately, this research underscores the urgent need for policy-driven interventions that balance environmental protection with economic empowerment. Without comprehensive and coordinated action, the continued degradation of the Niger Delta environment will not only endanger human well-being but also erode the region's long-term developmental prospects.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following policy and practical recommendations are made:

Enhanced Environmental Oversight: The Federal Ministry of Environment, NESREA, and NOSDRA should strengthen surveillance and conduct regular air, water, and soil quality assessments in refining-prone areas, with transparent reporting to ensure accountability.

Promotion of Sustainable Livelihoods: Government and oil companies should provide viable alternatives such as aquaculture, renewable energy enterprises, and agro-processing, supported by technical training and micro-credit to discourage youth involvement in illegal refining.

Community-Led Environmental Management: Empowering local communities through participatory governance involving traditional leaders, youth, and civil society can improve compliance, enhance local monitoring, and foster shared responsibility for environmental protection.

Restoration of Polluted Ecosystems: Polluted sites should be remediated urgently, especially in high-impact zones. Agencies like HYPREP should scale up ecosystem restoration using nature-based and sustainable land-use approaches.

Integrated Policy Synergy: A coordinated policy framework aligning the roles of NNPC, HYPREP, NOSDRA, and state environmental ministries is needed to harmonize environmental, social, and economic policies for sustainable regional development.

Environmental Education and Awareness: Targeted public campaigns, school programs, and media engagement should raise awareness about the ecological and health risks of artisanal refining while promoting sustainable livelihood practices.

5.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to existing literature by providing empirical evidence from a multistate primary survey, covering all nine Niger Delta oil producing states. It extends previous studies that focused on localized impacts by offering a comprehensive regional perspective and by integrating environmental degradation indicators air, water and soil within a single analytical framework. The results serve as a scientific baseline for policymakers, environmentalists, and

researchers in designing effective interventions for environmental sustainability in oil-producing regions.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Research

Future research should explore the economic valuation of the environmental costs associated with artisanal crude oil refining in the Niger Delta. This will help quantify the true financial burden of degradation on public health, agriculture, and biodiversity. In addition, comparative studies between regulated and unregulated refining communities could provide further insights into the effectiveness of policy interventions and community engagement strategies.

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